

in transplanted Bhutahi in a deepwater field. Vector green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens* populations had been increasing during July. The disease later spread to varietal demonstration plots and other yield evaluation trials. The disease diagnosis was confirmed by the virologist, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack.

No control measures were taken. Disease incidence was so severe that yields from some varieties were very low. Released and promising varieties were scored for resistance to tungro according to the Standard Evaluation System for Rice (Table 1).

In the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Program, severe infection occurred in 2 trials, PVT3 and PVT4 with 128 entries grown in 2 replications in each trial. Four entries from the RP1125 cross (RPW6-13/Ptb 2) showed

resistance, another 11 showed moderate resistance, and 15 were intermediate (Table 2). All others were susceptible to highly susceptible.

Tungro reappeared at Pusa and Patna during 1981-82 kharif.

Varietal recommendations for North and South Bihar, where tungro occurrence is becoming a problem, have been changed. Depending upon land situations, the newly recommended varieties are Pusa 2-21 and CR44-35 for dryland transplanting, Ratna and Rajendra Dhan 201 for midland transplanting, BR34 for wetland rainfed, and Janaki for semideep water.

Few resistant lines are available for wetland irrigated fields. Two lines, IET6263 (CR262-19) and RP1045-403, have been found promising. Resistant BR9 and Katarni — fragrant, short-slim, photoperiod-sensitive rices —

Table 2. PVT3 and PVT4 entries with resistance to rice tungro virus at Bihar, India.

Score ^a	Cultivars
1	RP1125-1526-2-1-1, RP1125-1526-2-2-3, RP1125-1526-3-2-4, RP1125-1528-1-4-3
3	CR161-42-16, CR186-1, CR236-63, CR276-5, RP1064-14-2-4, IR42, R8-2535, P837, P858, SKL6, Pusa 2-21
5	CR98-7216-CRP 34, CR149-9177-CRRP-19, CR188-10, RP974-29-3-2, RP1045-211-7-3-4, RP1064-14-2-3, RP1091-24, UPR243-63-1, AD9408, AD77496, P835, PY-1, Sonalee, RSB40

^a1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale of 0-9: 1 = less than 1% incidence, 5 = 21-30%.

may be recommended. Type 3, the only variety recommended for export, has been found susceptible to tungro. ■

Identification of stable sources of resistance to blast in Nepal

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Use of modern Taiwanese ponlai varieties and high doses of nitrogen fertilizer, particularly in the temperate region of

the Kathmandu valley and in other hilly regions of Nepal, have resulted in blast becoming a major source of yield losses. It has been possible to identify blast-resistant sources by using IRRI mass-screening techniques (see table). These lines are used extensively in Nepalese rice breeding programs. During 1977-81, high levels of blast resistance were found in cultivars Tetep, Dawn, and Carreon

and in lines derived from crosses with them. Blast reactions were scored according to the Standard Evaluation System for Rice. ■

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Highly resistant entries observed in blast nurseries at 2 sites in Nepal.

Cultivar or line	Source of resistance	Blast score ^a									
		Khumaltar (1,327 m alt)					Parwanipur (100 m alt)				
		1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981
CIAT-ICA 5	Tetep	1	1	0	3	0	1	1	1	c	0
IR1544-238-2-3	Tetep	1	1	0	2	0	1	1	2	1	0
IR1416-128-5-8	Tetep	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	c	c
IR1416-1-42-2-3-3	Tetep	1	1	b	1	0	1	1	b	1	c
IR1905-PP11-29-4-61	Tetep	1	1	0	3	0	1	1	2	1	0
IR1905-81-3-1	Tetep	2	2	0	2	0	1	1	5	1	0
IR3259-5-160-3	Tetep	1	2	b	2	0	4	1	b	1	0
74-5461	Tetep	2	1	b	b	0	1	1	b	b	3
IR5533-56-1-12	Tetep, Carreon	1	1	0	1	0	3	1	3	5	0
IR5533-PP850-1	Tetep, Carreon	1	1	b	3	0	2	1	b	1	0
IR5533-PP854-1	Tetep, Carreon	1	1	b	1	0	3	1	b	1	0
IR9660-00948-1	Dawn	2	1	b	2	0	1	1	b	1	0
Tetep (check)		1	4	0	1	0	4	1	1	1	0
Carreon (check)		b	1	0	1	0	b	1	5	3	1
Dawn (check)		4	1	0	b	2	c	1	4	b	4
Sankharika (susceptible check)		9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
Pokhareli Masino (local resistant)		2	2	2	1	3	1	2	2	0	1
Chainan 2 (commercial)		8	7	5	6	6	3	1	3	4	5
Chainung 242 (commercial)		8	7	5	4	8	4	1	3	4	5
Taichung 176 (commercial)		8	9	5	7	8	4	3	1	4	6

^aStandard Evaluation System for Rice: 0 = no lesions, 9 = all leaves dead. ^bEntry not used. ^cMissing.